

The Subjectivity of Theory of Value: A Refutation of Marxist Economic Theory

Libertarian Hermit

Abstract

For Marxism, the labor theory of value is the general law that explains not only the capitalist system but also the foundation that justifies the exploitation and oppression of workers, since all the profit obtained by the capitalist comes from the unpaid labor or surplus labor of the workers—that is, surplus value. In this sense, it is also from the labor theory of value that Marxists justify the tendency of capitalism toward collapse. However, all these inferences from Marxism are erroneous. The reason is that the value of labor is determined by the law of supply and demand. In other words, the value of labor is subjective because it depends on its usefulness and scarcity in the market. This is because it is consumer demand that ultimately determines the price of goods in the market. Finally, the subjective value of market prices implies that the economy is not a material structure but an ideological one.

Keywords: Labor Theory of Value, Subjective Value, Idealism, Materialism, Austrian School of Economics, Marxism.

Marxist labor theory of value

The Marxist labor theory of value posits that the profit earned by the entrepreneur from the sale of consumer goods produced by their employees is not determined by the law of supply and demand, but rather by the amount of labor time for which workers do not receive their wages. Therefore, all profit earned by the capitalist is a consequence of the exploitation and oppression of their workers, who labor for free during a certain segment of the workday. To understand this Marxist premise, it is necessary to address Marx's division of the workday, which he divided into necessary labor, which is paid working time, and surplus labor, which is the working time that the worker performs for free for the employer:

“Suppose the working day consists of 6 hours of necessary labour, and 6 hours of surplus labour. Then the free labourer gives the capitalist every week 6 x 6 or 36 hours of surplus labour. It is the same as if he worked 3 days in the week for himself, and 3 days in the week gratis for the capitalist” (Marx, 1996: 244-245).

The artificial division that Marx established between what he calls necessary labor and surplus labor is the theoretical framework that serves as justification for him to argue that surplus labor is the cause that sets the price of consumer goods in the market, since the profit of the entrepreneur does not come from the speculation of the free market, but from the value created by the worker, and that the entrepreneur unjustly expropriates. In that sense, it can be inferred that, for Marx, the scarcity of a good in relation to its demand in the market is not the cause that determines the price of goods. In other words, Marx believed that neither the abundance or scarcity of goods, nor the consumer’s subjective valuation, is a determining factor in price setting. For Marx, the price is determined solely by the amount of labor time that workers dedicated unpaid to its production— that is, surplus labor.

Thus, the profit that the entrepreneur obtains from the final sale of the goods in the market corresponds to what Marx called “surplus value”, which is the value produced by the surplus labor of the workers. According to Marx, surplus value is the determining economic factor that differentiates the value of a product between its production cost and its final value. In other words, the production cost is the price without the inclusion of surplus value, while the final price of a good is the sum of the production cost and the surplus value. Marx expressed the theory of surplus value mathematically as follows:

“At first then, $C = c + v$: for example, if £500 is the capital advanced, its components may be such that the £500 = £410 const. + £90 var. When the process of production is finished, we get a commodity whose value = $(c + v) + s$, where s is the surplus value; or taking our former figures, the value of this commodity may be (£410 const. + 90 var.) + £90 surpl. The original capital has now changed from C to C' , from £500 to £590” (Marx, 1996: 221).

The formula that Marx used to calculate the cost of production is $C = c + v$, where C is the total cost of producing a good, which is composed of two factors: constant capital (c) and variable capital (v). Constant capital refers to the means of production, raw materials, and other elements used in the production that are owned by the entrepreneur; variable capital, on the other hand, refers to the economic cost of the labor power of the workers employed in production. However, variable capital does not refer to all the hours of the working day, but only to the hours of necessary labor. But when the price of surplus labor, that is, surplus value, is integrated into the equation, the price of a good corresponds to its final market price, a price that is not determined by the law of supply and demand. In other words, Marx’s formula for the final market price of a good is $C = (c + v) + s$.

Nevertheless, Marx not only used the labor theory of value to mathematically justify that the price of a good is not subjectively determined by the law of supply and demand; he also used his theory

of surplus value to support the idea that the profit of entrepreneurs tends to decrease proportionally when constant capital (machines or means of production) replaces human labor (variable capital). This means that the surplus value of goods decreases as an entrepreneur reduces the use of human labor in production. For this reason, Marx called this theory “the law of the tendency of the rate profit to fall”, and in his words it was explained as follows:

“(…) then the gradual growth of constant capital in relation to variable capital must necessarily lead to a gradual fall of the general rate of profit, so long as the rate of surplus value, or the intensity of exploitation of labour by capital, remain the same” (Marx, 1998: 210).

To better understand this law, which Marx used as the definitive argument to support the thesis of the self-destructive tendency of capitalism, it must be applied to the case of an industry in which all processes are automated, without the direct intervention of human labor in production. This instance is fundamental to understanding the contradiction of the labor theory of value and the law of the tendency of the rate of profit to fall, since it necessarily follows that in a fully automated industry, the entrepreneur would obtain zero profit from the work of their machines. In other words, according to Marx’s reasoning, an entrepreneur would increase their profits by replacing human labor with automated machines. Thus, Marx implicitly posits that machine work is what impoverishes entrepreneurs. Therefore, a fully automated company run by artificial intelligence would not generate any profit for its owners. It could be said that, for Marx, the best thing would be to destroy the machines and return to the Stone Age.

Errors of the Marxist theory of value

Although the labor theory of value and the law of the tendency of the rate of profit to fall are completely wrong theories, the only thing that can be inferred as a reason that forced Marx to postulate all these inconsistencies, as economic theories that explain the development of capitalism, was his ideological and strategic objective of justifying, in an absolute way, that all the wealth produced in capitalism is due exclusively to the exploitation and oppression of the workers, which gives the irrefutable argument for the need for the communist revolution. However, as is evident, the entire Marxist economic theory is entirely false. The first Marx’s mistake was asserting that the market value of a good is determined by its utility and labor¹, without considering that, aside from utility, what truly determines the economic value of things is their scarcity. He failed to take into account that essential goods for life, such as air, are excessively abundant, which explains why this natural resource can be consumed freely without effort.

¹ For Marx, the price of a good is determined by its utility and scarcity. Regarding the first factor, he stated the following: “The utility of a thing makes it a use value” (Marx, 1996: 46). Regarding the second factor, which is the quantity of labor, Marx said the following: “How, then, is the magnitude of this value to be measured? Plainly, by the quantity of the value-creating substance, the labour, contained in the article. The quantity of labour, however, is measured by its duration, and labour time in its turn finds standard in weeks, days, and hours” (Marx, 1996: 48-49). However, no reference was made to the influence of scarcity on the price of a good.

But this theoretical inference by Marx is not his own; rather, it is a reinterpretation of the economic theory of David Ricardo, who was the intellectual framework that Marx used to construct his failed economic theory of capitalism, since he was the leading exponent of the English school of economics:

“Ricardo’s system, posing a principle that ‘the relative value of commodities depends exclusively on the amount of labour required for their production’, dates from 1817. Ricardo is the head of a whole school dominant in England since the Restoration” (Marx, 1996: 121).

The problem with Marx’s assertion is that it completely distorted Ricardo’s theory of value, since for Ricardo the value of labor was not an absolute value that held true in all cases. Rather, in some circumstances, the price of goods in the market depended exclusively on their scarcity, without the value of labor being one of the determining factors.² Therefore, the value of labor was a relative factor, not an absolute one as Marx postulated. Regarding this, Ricardo described the relativity of the value of labor as follows:

“There are some commodities, the value of which is determined by their scarcity alone. No labour can increase the quantity of such goods, and therefore their value cannot be lowered by an increased supply. Some rare statues and pictures, scarce books and coins, wines of a peculiar quality, which can be made only from grapes grown on a particular soil, of which there is a very limited quantity, are all of this description. Their value is wholly independent of the quantity of labour originally necessary to produce them, and varies with the varying wealth and inclinations of those who are desirous to possess them” (Ricardo, 1984: 6).

This statement by Ricardo is fundamental, because demonstrates that Marx made a biased interpretation of the cause of price in the market. Ricardo leaves no doubt that the market price of many consumer goods depends exclusively on their scarcity, and therefore their price is determined by the law of supply and demand. In other words, the market value of goods is subjective. Despite this, Ricardo still maintained the value of labor as one of the factors that influence the price of goods. However, unlike Marx, Ricardo did explicitly state that scarcity is a determining factor in the price of goods, which implies that he employed one of the fundamental principles of marginalist economic theory. The above, in Ricardo’s words: “Possessing utility, commodities derive their exchangeable value from two sources: from their scarcity, and from the quantity of labour required to obtain them” (Ricardo, 1984: 5).

Thus, it becomes clear that Marx did not fully employ Ricardo’s theory of value. If he did not consider the scarcity of a good in his economic theory, it is precisely because scarcity is the reason

² Among the main representatives of the Austrian School of economics, Böhm-Bawerk was the only one who exposed this contradiction in Ricardo’s theory of value: “He [Ricardo] begins his Principles with the express assertion that the Exchange value of goods has its origin in two sources—in their scarcity and in the quantity of labor that their production has cost. Certain goods, such as rare statues and paintings, get their value exclusively from the former source, and it is only the value of those goods that can be multiplied, without any assignable limit, by labour, which is determined by the amount of labour they cost” (Böhm-Bawerk, 1890: 376)

why the price of a good fluctuates independently of the amount of labor invested in its production. Therefore, if Marx had integrated the scarcity factor into his economic theory, the labor theory of value would have lost its entire foundation, and with it, the justification for the theory of the exploitation of the worker through surplus value. However, the labor theory of value is inherently contradictory, since the value of labor does not possess an objective value that can serve as a universal measure to quantify it. On the contrary, the value of labor is determined by the law of supply and demand like any other consumer good, since labor power is a good that is “consumed” by the entrepreneurs.

Despite the fluctuation in the market value of labor, Marx argued that the value of labor has a minimum limit that cannot fall further. This value corresponds to the necessary means of consumption that ensure the worker’s subsistence; that is, the minimum wage is equivalent to all those essential goods a worker needs to avoid inanition:

“The minimum limit of the value of labour power is determined by the value of the commodities, without the daily supply of which the labourer cannot renew his vital energy, consequently by the value of those means of subsistence that are physically indispensable” (Marx, 1996: 183).

The problem with the concept of minimum wage in Marx is that it is a value that cannot be objectively determined, but on the contrary, what is indispensable for life is nothing more than a subjective valuation that does not represent the intrinsic value of labor. Therefore, the minimum limit of labor is nothing other than the minimum wage offered by the market, according to the law of supply and demand. And this idea of Marx is simply a reproduction of Ricardo’s concept of the natural value of labor, since Ricardo classified the value of labor into its natural value and its market value:

“Labour, like all other things which are purchased and sold, and which may be increased or diminished in quantity, has its natural and its market price. The natural price of labour is that price which is necessary to enable the labourers, one with another, to subsist and to perpetuate their race, without either increase or diminution” (Ricardo, 1984: 52).

An important point Ricardo makes is that the minimum labor price must be set at a level that prevents the working population from increasing or decreasing. He made this reference because he implicitly applied the law of supply and demand to labor. In other words, any increase or decrease in the working population will disrupt the equilibrium of the labor market, since a decrease in the number of workers in society implies an increase in wages, which negatively impacts entrepreneurs’ interests. Conversely, an increase in the working population implies a decrease in the minimum wage, which directly affects workers’ interests. Therefore, for the minimum labor value to be stable, the number of workers available in the market must remain constant over time. In other words, the value of labor is as subjective as the price of any other consumer good in the market, and as such, it is useless for determining the market price of goods.

Consequently, the value of labor can only be established according to the law of supply and demand. However, Marx resisted accepting this scientific law of economics. In this sense, Marx asserted that the law of supply and demand is merely a fluctuation that does not fully determine the market price of labor, because, when the equilibrium point between the supply and demand of labor power is reached, the value of labor acquires its “natural” price, and therefore the law of supply and demand loses all impact on the determination of the price of labor in the market:

“Classical political economy borrowed from everyday life the category ‘price of labour’ without further criticism, and then simply asked the question, how is this price determined? It soon recognized that the change in the relations of demand and supply explained in regard to the price of labour, as of all other commodities, nothing except its changes, i.e., the oscillations of the market-price above or below a certain mean. If demand and supply balance, the oscillation of prices ceases, all other conditions remaining the same. But then demand and supply also cease to explain anything. The price of labour, at the moment when demand and supply are in equilibrium, is its natural price, determined independently of the relation of demand and supply” (Marx, 1996: 537-538).

Marx’s rejection of the universal nature of the law of supply and demand serves to justify the idea that labor possesses an intrinsic value independent of price fluctuations caused by supply and demand. Otherwise, Marx would have been forced to acknowledge that labor has no objective value, and therefore it is not workers who create value, but rather consumers demand, which ultimately determines whether a good is purchased in the market. In other words, for Marx, the law of supply and demand was the negation of his labor theory of value and his theory of surplus value, and the minimum limit of the value of labor, which is its natural price, was the sole basis from which the value of labor derived an objective value. But this is not the case in the economic laws of the market. Labor does not possess natural value, but rather only a market price determined by the law of supply and demand.

Böhm-Bawerk’s refutation of the Marxist theory of value

The value of labor, like any other consumer good, is essentially subjective, since it is determined only by two factors: its utility and its scarcity in the market. This fact was stated by Böhm-Bawerk: “It comes nearly to the same thing, only in a less precise form, to say: Usefulness and Scarcity are the ultimate determinants of the value of goods” (Böhm-Bawerk, 1930: 159). The utility of a good is subjectively determined by consumer demand. It is the consumer who decides whether consumer goods are useful to them in the market. Thus, the amount of labor that workers dedicate to the production of goods is irrelevant, because if it is not useful to the consumer, it will have no value in the market. And if a good is not demanded in the market, the labor also has no value. Therefore, the value of labor depends indirectly on consumer demand. On the other hand, the scarcity of goods is determined by the existing supply in the market. Good will be scarce or abundant in the market depending on the amount of demand. The greater the demand for a good compared to its

supply, the greater its scarcity, and therefore the higher its price. Conversely, the greater the supply of goods compared to the amount of consumer demand, the lower its price.

Consequently, the relationship between the utility and scarcity of a good is simply the interplay between the supply of goods and its demand in the market. In other words, the utility of goods is determined by consumer demand, and its scarcity is determined by the producer. In this sense, the law of supply and demand is the law that determines how prices are set in the market according to the interaction between the degree of scarcity and the demand for its utility. This means that suppliers will try to sell their product at the highest possible price, while consumers will try to buy goods at the lowest possible price:

“From this we get an important rule. An exchange is economically possible only between persons who put a different value, even an opposite value, upon the commodity and upon the price equivalent. The buyer must put a higher, the seller a lower, estimate on the commodity than he does on the equivalent” (Böhm-Bawerk, 1930: 195).

Thus, from the law of supply and demand, it is concluded that the market can take two specific forms: a supply-driven market and a demand-driven market. When supply exceeds demand, it implies high competition among suppliers in the market, which is benefits to consumers because prices tend to fall. This means that greater competition among sellers leads to lower prices. However, when demand exceeds supply prices tend to rise, which benefits sellers. Therefore, consumers will always prefer high competition in the market, while suppliers will always prefer the absence of competition. However, even though market prices are established through competition, the price itself is the inevitable result of individual valuations; that is, the market price of goods is determined by the subjectivity of individuals. In other words, since goods do not have an objective market price, the only way to establish them is through negotiation, which occurs when the consumer is willing to pay the price demanded by the seller, or vice versa, when the seller accepts the price that the consumer is willing to pay.

Marx is completely wrong when he claims that goods that have the same price in the market have that price because they possess the same amount of labor: “Commodities, therefore, in which equal quantities of labour are embodied, or which can be produced in the same time, have the same value” (Marx, 1996: 49). If different goods in the market have the same price, this is explained exclusively by the subjective valuation of individuals according to the law of supply and demand. This not only implies that goods of the same price require different quantities of labor, but also that higher-priced goods may require less time to produce. Therefore, the amount of labor only indicates the time it took to manufacture a good. In other words, the amount of labor only refers to the efficiency with which it is produced, while its market price is set subjectively.

The fact that the utility of a good is subjective means that is the individual who personally assesses whether the material properties of a consumer good meet their expectations for satisfying their needs. It is irrelevant whether a produced good fulfills its intended function; if the consumer determines that the good is unsuitable for satisfying their needs, the function of the good is

subjectively valued as useless. Therefore, what determines the market price of a good is not its objective value³, but the subjective value of that good for the consumer. In this sense, Böhm-Bawerk defined the concept of the subjective value of a good as the personal criterion that an individual applies to determines the suitability of a good for the satisfaction of their needs, which is linked to the pleasure that the good can give:

“Value in the Subjective sense is the importance which a good, or a complex of goods, possess with regard to the well-being of a subject. In this sense I should say of any particular good that it was valuable to me, if I recognized that my wellbeing was so associated with it that the possession of it satisfied some want, secured me a gratification or a feeling of pleasure which I should not have had without it, or saved me from a pain which, otherwise, I should have had to endure. In this case the existence of the good means my gain, the absence of it my loss, in wellbeing: to me it is a matter of importance, for me it has value” (Böhm-Bawerk, 1930: 130).

Böhm-Bawerk’s distinction between subjective and objective value is the theoretical framework that refutes the Marxist distinction between use value and exchange value. It is from the concept of subjective value that Böhm-Bawerk demonstrated that use value is not an objective value, but rather a subjective value that the individual determines according to the pleasure or satisfaction it provides. Therefore, use value is the subjective utility of a good. Regarding exchange value, Böhm-Bawerk maintained that it is the subjective value of a good quantified by its market price; that is, exchange value is the price determined by the law of supply and demand. In other words, use value is the subjective value that the individual attributes to a good, while exchange value is the subjective value determined by social relations in the market. Böhm-Bawerk’s refutation of the Marxist concept of use value and exchange value is as follows:

“Understood in a certain sense, to which in this place we shall adhere, both of these – exchange value as well as use value – are kinds of subjective value. Use value is the importance which a good obtains for the welfare of a person, on the assumption that it is used immediately in furthering his wellbeing; and, similarly, exchange value is the importance which a good obtains for the welfare of a person through its capacity to procure other goods by way of barter” (Böhm-Bawerk, 1930: 166)

Therefore, the Marxist categories of use value and exchange value of goods are subjective values, demonstrating that the price of a good cannot be determined by the amount of labor.

³ The objective value of a consumer good is its material properties or physical capacity to satisfy a need. Böhm-Bawerk defined objective value as follows: “By Objective value, on the other hand, is meant the Power or Capacity of a good to procure some one objective result. In this sense there are as many kinds of value as there are external results with which man may be connected” (Böhm-Bawerk, 1930: 130)

The failure of the Marxist critique of Böhm-Bawerk

Within the intellectual sphere of Marxism, Böhm-Bawerk's refutation of the concepts of use and exchange value did not go unnoticed. In response, Nicolai Bukharin criticized Böhm-Bawerk's concepts of objective value and the psychologism of the Austrian school of economics:

“Even from the point of view Böhm-Bawerk, his assertion could not be defended, at bottom. If the objective value is nothing more or less than a resultant of the subjective evaluations, it must not be grouped with the chemical and physical properties of commodities. On the other hand, it differs from them in principle: it contains not an “atom of matter”, being descended from and shaped by immaterial factors, namely, the individual evaluations of the various “economic subjects”. However peculiar this may sound, we must nevertheless point out that the pure psychologism so characteristic of the Austrian School and of Böhm-Bawerk is perfectly compatible with a vulgar, excessively materialistic naïve and uncritical” (Bukharin, 1970: 63).

According to the arguments that Bukharin used in his refutation of Böhm-Bawerk, it is evident that he did not understand the distinction between objective and subjective value. Bukharin erred in asserting that objective value arises from the subjective value. On the contrary, Böhm-Bawerk made it clear that the objective value of good is independent of the subjective valuations of the individual; the physical properties of a good exist independently of consciousness. However, Bukharin's assertion can be clarified by considering the context of the philosophical dispute between Marxism and idealism. In this sense, the Marxist philosopher Konstantinov expressed the theoretical conflict between Marxist materialism and bourgeois idealism in the fact that the former postulates that matter determines consciousness; on the contrary, idealism postulates that consciousness determines matter:

“Idealism, as we have seen, proceeds from the assumption that the material is a product of the spiritual. Materialism, on the contrary, begins from the assumption that the spiritual is a product of the material. Both these views are of a monistic character, that is to say, they proceed from one definite principle” (Konstantinov, 1982: 19-20).

It is from Konstantinov's definition of materialism and idealism that Bukharin's critique of Böhm-Bawerk's concepts of objective and subjective value is derived. Since the Austria school of economics maintains that the price of goods in the market is subjective, Bukharin applied the monistic principle of idealism to assert that the objective value defined by Böhm-Bawerk cannot be objective, because it is a value determined by the subjective value. However, the theoretical framework of the Austrian school of economics does not correspond to the monistic idealism attributed it by Marxists, but rather is founded on the dualist principle, meaning that ideas have a causal system different from that of matter. While it is undeniable that consciousness originated from matter, the ideas of consciousness related to the sphere of values, also called “axiology”, are

a type of object entirely opposed to material objects. It can be said that the social sciences are axiological sciences and therefore cannot belong to the sphere of the natural sciences.

The epistemic dualism that separates the sphere of the social sciences from the natural sciences was demonstrated by the philosopher Heinrich Rickert. On the one hand, the objects of the natural sciences are objects of perception, that is, they can be perceived through the senses of the human body; on the other hand, the objects of the social sciences can only be perceived through consciousness, since they are all those objects that have meaning, utility, or purpose— that is, they are values. This distinction between the objects of study of the natural and social sciences was explained by Rickert as follows:

“The crucial question in drawing the distinction between the cultural and the natural sciences is what the opposite of understanding is conceived to be. We must distinguish it from perceiving and in so doing conceive the latter idea so broadly that the entire world accessible to the senses (i.e., all immediately given physical and psychical events) will be considered as the object of perception. But even then, in the interest of logical clarity, we cannot rest content with the acts of the subject who does the understanding. On the contrary, from the methodological point of view it is the objects which are understood that are essential. If the entire world of phenomena directly accessible to the senses is designated as the object of perception, then only nonsensorial meanings or complexes of meaning remain as objects of understanding, if this word is to retain any precise signification. (...) But with this distinction between perceivable and understandable objects we have again approached our previous antithesis between nature and culture. Because understandable meanings and complexes of meaning are found only together with perceivable objects, we can also say: the objects of science are, on the one hand, those which, like cultural phenomena, have an importance or a meaning and which we wish to understand for the sake of this importance and this meaning; and, on the other hand, those which, like the phenomena of nature, are regarded as completely devoid of importance and meaning and which therefore remain incapable of being understood” (Rickert, 1962: 20).

In this sense, the objective and subjective value defined by Böhm-Bawerk belong, respectively, to the sphere of natural and social science. Therefore, objective value does not derive from subjective values, as Bukharin erroneously maintained. This is because the Austrian school of economics establishes that the objects of the social sciences are independent of the natural sciences. The latter demonstrates that the science of human action, or praxeology, is a science that is based on the study of causality between means and ends. Thus, human action is teleological and not mechanistic as in the natural sciences. Mises expressed this fact in the following way:

“However, the sciences of human action differ radically from the natural sciences. All authors eager to construct an epistemological system of the sciences of human action according to the pattern of the natural sciences err lamentably” (Mises, 1998: 39).

Nevertheless, Marxism commits precisely the theoretical error against which Mises warned: treating the social sciences as natural sciences. The Marxism error lies in its materialist conception

of economics, and in making it the theoretical basis for explaining the causes of ideas in society, according to the logic of mechanistic causality of natural sciences. In that sense, Bukharin argued that human action is subject to deterministic causality, just like matter, so there is no principle of indeterminism of free will:

“In our consideration of the question of the human will, the question whether it is free, or determined by certain causes, like everything else in the world, we arrived at the conclusion that we must adopt the point of view of determinism” (Bukharin, 1933: 53).

This means that Marxism posits that human action is not teleological, as praxeology clearly demonstrates; on the contrary, social phenomena can only be explained through natural causality, which implies that the social sciences share the epistemological basis as the natural sciences. For this reason, Marxist materialism establishes that the social sciences are methodologically dependent on the natural sciences, a fact derived from the idea that consciousness, the ideology, is causally determined by matter. Bukharin expressed the Marxist materialist interpretation of the social sciences as follows:

“In a word, as soon as we wish really to understand social phenomena, we immediately find ourselves asking the question: “why?” i.e., we ask concerning the causes of these phenomena, in spite of the fact that these phenomena may be the expressions of certain human purposes. In other words, even if men should regulate everything consciously, and even if everything should be accomplished in society just as these men desire, we should still need an explanation of social phenomena, not teleology, but a consideration of the causes of the phenomena, i.e., the determination of a cause and effect relation, as their law. And for this reason, there is no difference at all in this regard between the social sciences concerned with nature” (Bukharin, 1933: 29).

Despite Marxist critiques of the teleological or idealist method in the social sciences, these arguments are inherently inconsistent and therefore entirely erroneous. Praxeology demonstrates that human action is determined by the ends that individuals freely choose to achieve. Thus, its causality is not mechanistic-natural, but rather goal-oriented. In this sense, the economy is not a material structure causally determined by the means of production, rather, production itself is independent of the economic activity of individuals. In other words, the economy is determined by the subjective valuations of individuals, meaning that the economy is not only an ideological system like politics and legal; it also implies that the economy is the exchange of property that individuals make in the market. This means that the economy is determined by property rights, which implies that, if the logic structure-superstructure is maintained, the economy is the ideological superstructure and politics its ideological structural base that creates the social existence of individuals (Libertarian Hermit, 2026: 2-3).

Therefore, the social sciences cannot be approached from a materialist point of view, just as the natural sciences cannot be explained from an idealist point of view. In other words, the social sciences are methodologically idealist, and the natural sciences are methodologically materialist.

Conclusion

The Marxist labor theory of value is nothing more than an attempt to justify the materialist interpretation of human activity. Labor theory of value is the theoretical justification that Marxism uses to demonstrate that the economy is not teleologically determined by the subjective valuations of individuals, but rather that the mechanistic activity of labor is the material foundation that determines the price of goods in the market. It also justifies the theory of the exploitation and oppression of workers, since the entrepreneur profit comes exclusively from the unpaid labor of the workers, or surplus labor; that is, the entrepreneur enriches himself by stealing the surplus value created by the workers. Finally, labor theory justifies the supposed tendency of capitalism toward collapse, because the continuous substitution of human labor by machines reduces the entrepreneur's profits and increases production costs.

Nevertheless, the Marxist labor theory of value is entirely false. First, labor, like any other good, has its price subjectively determined by the law of supply and demand. The division of the workday into necessary labor and surplus labor is also false, since the employer pays for the entire workday. The ideas of surplus labor and surplus value are nothing more than nonexistent categories in the organization of production. The price of a good depends exclusively on consumer demand. No matter what price the producer sets in the market; if the consumer subjectively values that good as useless, it will have no value because there will be no demand. Although the consumer good is produced by the worker, its final price is determined by consumer demand. Therefore, both the worker and the employer are subject to the will of the consumer.

Thus, if Marxism remains obstinate in defending Marx's labor theory of value and denying the scientific validity of the Austrian school economic theory, it is solely due to the political interest in maintaining the revolutionary ideal and continuing to secure its privileged position in academia. Otherwise, it would lose its intellectual and cultural hegemony.

Bibliography

Böhm-Bawerk, Eugen von. *The Positive Theory of Capital*. New York: G. E. Stechert & Co., 1930.

Bukharin, Nikolai (1933). *Historical Materialism: A System of Sociology*. New York: International Publishers.

Bukharin, Nikolai. (1970). *The Economic Theory of the Leisure Class*. New York: Augustus M. Kelley Publishers.

Heinrich, Rickert (1962). *Science and History. A critique of positivist epistemology*. Princeton: D. Van Nostrand Company, Inc.

Konstantinov, F. V. (ed.). (1982). *The Fundamentals of the Marxist-Leninist Philosophy*. Moscow: Progress Publishers.

Libertarian Hermit (2026). *Right-Libertarian Theory of History. Part I: A refutation of Marxist Historical Materialism*. *The Marginalist Journal*, Volume 1, pp. 1-7.

Marx, Karl (1996). *Capital. A Critique of Political Economy. Volume I*. In Marx & Engels *Collected Works Vol. 35*. London: Lawrence & Wishart.

Marx, Karl. (1998). *Capital. A Critique of Political Economy. Volume III*. In Marx & Engels *Collected Works Vol. 37*. London: Lawrence & Wishart.

Mises, Ludwig von (1998). *Human Action: A Treatise on Economics*. Auburn: Ludwig von Mises Institute, 1998.

Ricardo, David (1984). *The principles of Political Economy and Taxation*. London: Guernsey Press.